

INVESTIGATION OF RIGIDITY INDICATORS OF PACKAGE STRUCTURES IN SPINNING MACHINES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17907092>

Abstract. Composite structures consisting of a package of assembled flat elements are widely used in spinning machines in textile enterprises. They can be used as working parts or load-bearing elements. This article addresses the issue of phenomenological determination of the rigidity indicators of these structures.

Key words: composite structures, flat element package, bending rigidity, longitudinal rigidity, torsional rigidity.

Annotatsiya. To'qimachilik korxonalarida qo'llaniladigan yigiruv mashinalarida jamlangan yassi elementlar paketidan tashkil topgan tarkibli konstruksiyalar keng qo'llaniladi. Ular ishchi organlar yoki tashuvchi elementlar sifatida qo'llanilishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada konstruksiyalarning bikrlilik ko'rsatkichlarini fenomenologik aniqlash masalasi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tarkibli konstruksiyalar, yassi elementlar paketi, egilishdagi bikrlilik, buylama bikrlilik, aylanma bikrlilik.

Аннотация. Композитные конструкции, состоящие из пакета сборных плоских элементов, широко применяются в прядильных машинах текстильных предприятий. Они могут использоваться в качестве рабочих органов или силовых элементов. В данной статье рассматривается вопрос феноменологического определения показателей жёсткости конструкций

Ключевые слова: композитные конструкции, пакет плоских элементов, особенность при изгибе, особенность при кручении, особенность при вращении.

Introduction. Structural constructions used in various industry sectors are divided into two groups based on their function: constructions used as support (load-bearing) elements and constructions used as working components. Structural constructions belonging to both groups

can also be classified into two types based on their operating principle: those that do not use force factors for structural purposes and those that do.

Force factors can be applied in structural constructions to increase their durability and rigidity. This can be achieved through elastic reinforcement, press fitting (interference fits) to create a rigid spatial structure, as well as by forming packages composed of multiple elements that can operate under tension, compression, bending, and torsion. For this purpose, force factors are applied longitudinally, transversely (including radially), and as moments [1,2].

Meeting both technological and structural requirements simultaneously in modern constructions is a complex task. Successfully solving this problem requires the use of unconventional approaches. One such approach is optimal design. The distinctive feature of optimal design is that, based on given initial parameters or constraints, the optimal or extreme values of certain parameters such as weight or cost are determined. With the increase in the number of factors considered and the growing demands for design accuracy, the need to precisely identify factors of various physical natures has arisen.

In mechanical engineering, construction, and spacecraft, structural constructions made of flat element packages compressed by a special tensioning cable are used. These elements may be identical in shape and size or vary according to certain rules, and they can be made from the same or different materials. The main purpose of such constructions is to increase the stiffness parameters of the support elements and working parts of machines.

In modern textile industry technological machines, working elements often consist of a package of flat, disk-shaped elements. This package is assembled on a shaft and reinforced by longitudinal compressive force. Some studies indicate that the pneumatic-mechanical spinning method is promising. The most common equipment in this system is the disk spinning chamber.

One of the important working elements of spinning machines is the discrete drum (see Figure 1), which is assembled from disks of two different diameters [3,4]. The disk assembly alternately creates gaps and clearances, all of which have the same width. The disks are compressed longitudinally by compression nuts, forming a package that can withstand tensile, compressive, bending, and torsional forces. The main mechanical parameters of the cylinder include stiffness in longitudinal, bending, and torsional directions. It is known that these parameters consist of the combined stiffness of the shaft and the disk package. Methods for calculating the stiffness parameters of the shaft are known [5], so it is sufficient to determine the stiffness parameters of the disk package.

However, the mechanics of such layered constructions have not been sufficiently developed because there is currently no reliable, scientifically based method to theoretically determine their stiffness parameters accurately and to identify the specific characteristics of dynamic processes.

Studying the behavior of layered constructions under bending, tension-compression, and torsion, as well as developing analytical methods to determine their stiffness parameters and analyzing the influence mechanisms of design and operational factors, presents a complex physical-mechanical problem. Highly simplified models yield low-accuracy results, while very complex models become practically inefficient due to the large number of factors and their varied effects on layered rods.

Currently, in the study of complex objects, methods such as diakoptics, finite element methods, and phenomenological approaches are considered effective. Diakoptics and finite

element methods are based on dividing the object into parts for study and require individual approaches or powerful computers.

Phenomenological analysis, on the other hand, is based on studying the object as a whole without dividing it into parts, allowing this approach to avoid deviating from the physical essence of the processes. For this reason, we study the behavior of flexible layered constructions under external influences based on phenomenological analysis. In this case, the layered compression or monolithic layered rods (formed by welding or bonding) are considered as theoretical models.

Research Methods. Our preliminary theoretical and experimental studies (also confirmed by other authors) show that as the compression force of the package increases from zero, the following phenomena are observed:

-The values of bending, longitudinal, and torsional stiffness indicators continuously increase. At the same time, the discrete stiffness values asymptotically approach those calculated for the monolithic layered rod.

-The growth rate of bending, longitudinal, and torsional stiffness decreases steadily from the maximum value at zero compression force and asymptotically approaches zero.

-According to experimental results, in some cases, either directly or at least through extrapolation, the compression force of the package can be determined at such values where the stiffness indicators differ from the values calculated by the MPS (monolithic layered rod) model by no more than a predetermined very small limited amount.

-The practical ranges of stiffness increase and the decrease in their growth rates are limited depending on the technical specifications and mechanical parameters of the layered rod.

From the above, the following conclusion can be drawn: at appropriate values of the package compression force, the growth rates of bending, longitudinal, and torsional stiffness of the GPS (porous layered rod) can, as a first approximation, be considered proportional to the difference between the calculated stiffness of the MPS monolithic layered rod and the stiffness of the GPS, and inversely proportional to the compression force values [3].

It should be emphasized that the compression force increases linearly over its entire range of variation $[0, N_0]$. Taking this fact into account, the value of the compression force can be assumed to be equal to the half-sum of its values at the boundary points of this range [4].

$$N = \frac{0 + N_0}{2} = \frac{N_0}{2} \quad (1)$$

Based on the above foundations, it is possible to mathematically investigate the variation processes of the longitudinal, bending, and torsional stiffness parameters of the package rod depending on changes in the package compression force values, as well as to develop mathematical models. The similarity in the variation patterns of the bending, longitudinal, and torsional stiffness of the GPS (porous package rod) allows for their simultaneous study.

Research results. According to the accepted main views and assumptions, with each change in the values of the package compression force, the increase in the values of the longitudinal, bending, and torsional stiffness follows the law: it is proportional to the difference between the corresponding MPS (monolithic package rod) stiffness values and the stiffness values, and inversely proportional to the average values of the package compression force.

$$dB_n = \frac{2(B_{pn} - B_n)}{N_o} dN \quad (2a)$$

$$dC_{II} = \frac{2(C_{pII} - C_{II})}{N_0} dN \quad (2b)$$

$$dD_k = \frac{2(D_{pk} - D_k)}{N_0} dN \quad (2s)$$

Here:

$dB_n, dC_i, dD_k, dB_n, dC_i, dD_k$ — increases in the longitudinal, bending, and torsional stiffness of the flexible package rod, respectively;

dN — increase in the value of the package compression force;

B_{pn} — calculated longitudinal stiffness for the monolithic package rod;

C_{pi} — calculated bending stiffness for the monolithic package rod;

D_{pk} — calculated torsional stiffness for the monolithic package rod;

B_n — current longitudinal stiffness of the package rod;

C_i — current bending stiffness of the package rod;

D_k — current torsional stiffness of the package rod;

N_0 — average value of the package compression force.

All other influencing factors not taken into account are also determined through the first functions A_n, A_u, A_n, A_u , and A_k, A_k , respectively, which for now are assumed to be constant (unchanging).

Thus, equations (2a), (2b), and (2c) can be rewritten in the following form:

$$dB_n = \frac{2A_n(B_{pn} - B_n)}{N_0} dN \quad (3a)$$

$$dC_{II} = \frac{2A_u(C_{pu} - C_u)}{N_0} dN \quad (3b)$$

$$dD_k = \frac{2A_k(D_{pk} - D_k)}{N_0} dN \quad (3s)$$

In these equations, the variables are separated.

$$\frac{dB_n}{dN} = \frac{2A_n(B_{pn} - B_n)}{N_0} \quad (4a)$$

$$\frac{dC_{II}}{dN} = \frac{2A_u(C_{pu} - C_u)}{N_0} \quad (4b)$$

$$\frac{dD_k}{dN} = \frac{2A_k(D_{pk} - D_k)}{N_0} \quad (4s)$$

At the same time, the obtained equations can be rewritten in the following form:

$$\frac{dB_n}{dN} + \frac{2A_n}{N_0} B_n - \frac{2A_n B_{pn}}{N_0} = 0 \quad (5a)$$

$$\frac{dC_{II}}{dN} + \frac{2A_u}{N_0} C_{II} - \frac{2A_u C_{pu}}{N_0} = 0 \quad (5b)$$

$$\frac{dD_k}{dN} + \frac{2A_k}{N_0} D_k - \frac{2A_k D_{pk}}{N_0} = 0 \quad (5s)$$

Equations (5a), (5b), and (5c) are first-order ordinary linear differential equations, and their general solutions can be written in the following form:

$$B_n = B_{pn} + C_1 e^{-\frac{2A_n N}{N_0}} \quad (6a)$$

$$C_{II} = C_{PII} + C_2 e^{-\frac{2A_u N}{N_0}} \quad (6b)$$

$$D_k = D_{pk} + C_3 e^{-\frac{2A_k N}{N_0}} \quad (6s)$$

To determine the integration constants, we formulate the boundary conditions in the following form:

Conditions: $N=0, B_n=0; N=0, C_{II}=0; N=0, D_k=0;$

From these, we find: $C_1 = B_{pn}; C_2 = C_{PII}; C_3 = D_{pk}.$

Thus, equations (6a), (6b), and (6c) take the following form:

$$B_n = B_{pn} (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_n N}{N_0}}) \quad (7a)$$

$$C_{II} = C_{PII} (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_u N}{N_0}}) \quad (7b)$$

$$D_k = D_{pk} (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_k N}{N_0}}) \quad (7s)$$

Now, for the longitudinal, bending, and torsional rigidities of the monolithic package rod, we use the solutions from formulas (2), (3), and (4), which are constructed alternately from working and spacer discs. Thus, based on phenomenological determination, the following expressions can be written for the values of longitudinal, bending, and torsional rigidities:

$$B_n = \frac{(l_p + l_n) E_p F_p E_n F_n}{l_n E_p F_p + l_p E_p F_p} (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_n N}{N_0}}) \quad (8a)$$

$$C_u = \frac{(l_p + l_n) E_p J_p E_n J_n}{l_n E_p J_p + l_p E_n J_n} (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_k N}{N_0}}) \quad (8b)$$

$$D_{pk} = \frac{(l_p + l_n) G_p J_{pp} G_n J_{pn}}{l_n G_p J_{pp} + G_p G_n J_{pn}} (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_k N}{N_0}}) \quad (8s)$$

Here:

- l_p, l_n — thicknesses of the working and spacer discs;

- E_p, E_n — elastic moduli of the materials of the working and spacer discs;

- J_{pp}, J_{pn} — polar moments of inertia of the cross-sectional areas of the working and spacer discs.

We accept the influence functions of the transverse force on the longitudinal, bending, and torsional stiffnesses (or briefly, the functions of longitudinal, bending, and torsional rigidities) in the following form:

$$\mu = (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_n N}{N_0}}) \quad (9a)$$

$$\eta = (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_u N}{N_0}}) \quad (9b)$$

$$\nu = (1 - e^{-\frac{2A_k N}{N_0}}) \quad (9s)$$

Then, equations (9a), (9b), and (9c) are expressed in the following form:

$$B_n = \mu \frac{(l_p + l_n)E_p F_p E_n F_n}{l_n E_p F_p + l_p E_p F_p} = \mu B_{pn} \quad (10a)$$

$$C_u = \eta \frac{(l_p + l_n)E_p L_p E_n J_n}{l_n E_n J_p + l_p E_n J_n} = \eta C_{pu} \quad (10b)$$

$$D_k = \nu \frac{(l_p + l_n)G_p J_{pp} G_n J_{pn}}{G_n G_p J_{pp} + G_p G_n J_{pn}} = \nu D_{pk} \quad (10s)$$

The obtained solutions describe both qualitatively and quantitatively the changes in longitudinal, bending, and torsional stiffness parameters of layered structures composed of flat elements.

Conclusion. The obtained solutions are important not only theoretically but also practically. They demonstrate how the longitudinal, bending, and torsional stiffness of layered structures (consisting of working and spacer elements) change qualitatively and quantitatively. This can be applied in:

-Designing layered rods, disk systems, transmission elements, and composite structures operating under various loads;

-Enhancing the vibration resistance of working components in spinning machines and ensuring energy efficiency.

Determining stiffness parameters through a phenomenological approach increases the reliability of constructions, extends their service life, and enables optimal material selection. Therefore, the results of this study can be used both in scientific research and practical design processes.

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